

A Geometrical Perspective on the Insulin Evolution

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Abstract : We study the molecular evolution of insulin from the metric geometry point of view. In mathematics, and particularly in geometry, distances and metrics between objects are of fundamental importance. Using a weaker notion than the classical distance, namely the weighted quasi-metrics, one can study the geometry of biological sequences (DNA, mRNA, or proteins) space. We analyze from the geometrical point of view a family of 60 insulin homologous sequences ranging on a large variety of living organisms from human to the nematode *C. elegans*. We show that the distances between sequences provide important information about the evolution and function of insulin.

Keywords : metric geometry, evolution, insulin, *C. elegans*

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